

D5.3

EMPOWER

deliverables

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In this deliverable, Work Package 5 presents the results of a series of semi-structured interviews they conducted with EMPOWER's ethical reflection team. These interviews document the challenges participants faced while working on the project, how they dealt with them, and what they would do differently given the opportunity. The deliverable also includes recommendations based on these interviews that WP5 developed to help other researchers working on projects like EMPOWER structure their research.

Description

WP.5

Work Package. 5(M30)

1.Introduction

Description	Authors
Auditing Report 2	Thomasin Coggins; Pim Haselager

In the previous two deliverables completed by Work Package 5, the authors Thomasin Coggins and Pim Haselager provided an ethical framework focused on self-esteem and recommendations designed to support all members of EMPOWER reflect on and improve research practices. They also included recommendations concerning how to responsibly develop and deploy educational technology for neurodiverse children. Both deliverables employed insights from the academic literature on participatory research design, the ethics of technology, disability studies, and neurodiversity rights as their primary source of inspiration. Additionally, they incorporated feedback from other members of EMPOWER to ensure that the content aligned with the project's goals and included feasible suggestions that EMPOWER members could incorporate into their pre-established workflows. Considering that we provided recommendations based on relevant literature in the previous two deliverables, we decided to extend our approach to develop and complete deliverable 5.3. As EMPOWER will conclude in roughly 6 months, we believe that we should now begin documenting the challenges EMPOWER members faced while working on the project, how they dealt with them, and what they would do differently given the opportunity. We will use these insights to build a selection of best practices that other researchers who wish to initiate similar projects to EMPOWER (e.g., ones dealing with the development of educational technologies for neurodiverse children) can use to guide their work. As such, these deliverables are or will be chiefly directed towards external researchers rather than EMPOWER members.

We will continue constructing these best practices in deliverable 5.4 and a research paper we plan to complete by Autumn 2025. As such, Deliverable 5.3 represents our initial efforts to translate lessons learnt from EMPOWER into recommendations. To develop this deliverable, we conducted semi-structured interviews with EMPOWER’s ethical reflection team and then interpreted this data via thematic analysis that observed Grounded Theory protocol (Charmaz, 2014). We designed these semi-structured interviews to elicit responses from participants that communicate the challenges they faced and the recommendations they would give to other researchers. We tailored the results section of this deliverable around these two overarching themes (challenges and recommendations). We provide our interpretations of these results in the discussion section of this deliverable. This analysis highlights the challenges and recommendations Work Package 5 believes anyone working on similar projects to EMPOWER should pay close attention to. This section also represents our initial efforts to develop “best practices” for projects like EMPOWER. We conclude the deliverable by explaining how we intend to use its results to develop more recommendations based on EMPOWER members’ experiences. We should also state that we decided to present the findings of the semi-structured interviews mentioned above in this deliverable to provide external researchers with practical advice regarding how to incorporate the recommendations we developed in deliverables 5.1 and 5.2 concerning the ethics of education and neurodiversity into their workflows. As such, we highly recommend that our readers consult these deliverables before reading this one (as they contain recommendations directly related to the ethics of education and neurodiversity).

2. Methods

During an EMPOWER meeting in October 2024, Work Package 5 presented their plans to interview ideally all EMPOWER members¹ to gather data concerning their experiences working on the project and translate this data into best practices. During this meeting, we decided to begin this project by interviewing EMPOWER’s ethical reflection team as they had already agreed to be other Work Packages’ primary liaisons regarding ethics. After the meeting, Work Package 5 developed the following interview guide structured around to a selection of themes we believed would elicit data rich enough to translate into best practice.

Theme	Question
Context Setting	Can you briefly summarize your role in EMPOWER?
Challenges: Collaboration	How does your research relate to other Work Packages' research (and vice-versa)?
Recommendations: Collaboration	Can you provide any recommendations for other researchers in this regard?
Challenges: Ethics	Have you followed any protocol regarding ethics? (these can be ones developed by WP5 or ones yet documented by EMPOWER)
Recommendations: Ethics	Can you provide any recommendations for other researchers in this regard?
Recommendations: General	If you could start the whole project again, what would you do differently?

¹ Aside from Thomasin Coggins as she was chosen to conduct the interviews.

Once drafted, we presented the interview guide to other EMPOWER members during a meeting in January 2025 to receive their feedback and approval. We then approached and scheduled the interviews with EMPOWER's ethical reflection team in January, February and March 2025 (n=7). We chose to begin with this low number of participants to test whether the interview guide elicited useful responses (e.g., provided data that covered the themes) from senior EMPOWER members who represented each Work Package. We sent the interview guide to the participants before the interview to help them to understand the general intent of the questions and to prepare their answers. The interviews took roughly 30 minutes to complete and, following typical Grounded Theory protocol (Charmaz, 2014) occasionally diverged from the interview guide to allow participants to discuss additional, relevant topics. All interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams and transcribed by the apps' in-built transcription software (alongside some minor manual transcription to deal errors created by the software). Thomasin Coggins conducted all the interviews.

After completing the interviews, we interpreted them via deductive thematic analysis (Thomas & Harden, 2004; Charmaz, 2014). As anticipated, they more-or-less aligned with the pre-established themes. After analyzing the transcripts, however, we developed a set of additional sub-themes that more closely conveyed the participants' stated experiences. We have structured the results section of this deliverable around these sub-themes that represent challenges and recommendations that participants commonly discussed during the interviews. Before presenting our results, it is necessary to highlight a notable confounding factor that almost certainly influenced the participants' responses. As stated earlier, Thomasin Coggins conducted all the interviews. Thomasin is a member of EMPOWER (Work Package 5), helped develop deliverables 5.1 and 5.2., and knew all participants collegially beforehand. As such, her presence may have encouraged the participants to avoid discussing topics they believed she would assess negatively. This was an unavoidable limitation of the research presented in this deliverable. One way around this would have been to invite an external researcher to conduct these interviews. However, this did mean that the interviewer and interviewees had an immediate rapport and knew about each other's research beforehand.

3.1. Results

We have divided the results sections into a 4x2 structure which represents the challenges the participants communicated to us and their recommendations for dealing with them. The structure of the interview guide thankfully did encourage participants to discuss the challenges they faced and then to provide recommendations to deal with them. Hence the inclusion of identical sub-themes in sections pertaining to challenges and recommendations. We have also included a 4x2 table summarizing this deliverable's results at the end of this section.

3.2.1. Challenges: abrupt beginning and conclusion

The participants frequently communicated that working on a project that conformed to standards determined by Horizon Europe sometimes hampered them from developing practices they believed could have benefitted EMPOWER. To be clear, none of them conveyed that they had ignored protocol (ethical or otherwise) demanded from such projects. Instead, they relayed that the Horizon Europe requires its funded projects to follow specific trajectories. For instance, it expects projects to have clearly defined beginnings, middles, and ends – that coincide with official checkpoints. The participants suggested that this model does not always lend itself to the type of research conducted by EMPOWER.

Several participants mentioned that Horizon Europe projects start and end too quickly. They suggested that the model outlined above encourages researchers to pursue independent goals immediately, leaving less time than desirable for them to learn about each other's expertise and establish means to collaborate. Indeed, EMPOWER's proposal includes clear commitments that each Work Package must fulfil at specific times. The participants implied that these commitments can hinder meaningful interaction and collaboration between Work Packages at the beginning of projects. One participant, who has worked on similar projects before, provided a provocative metaphor to describe this process. They stated that Work Packages begin as "islands" that cannot communicate with one another. Over time, the inhabitants of said islands "build bridges" to become a more unified collective. As "building bridges" takes considerable effort, Work Packages

often struggle to share their knowledge during a project's beginning and middle phases. Furthermore, inhabitants tend to finish building these bridges at the end of a project. Unfortunately, this means they become useless shortly after their completion – as everyone who uses them soon moves on to other things. We should state, though, that the project partners leading the work packages where the platform has been defined (WP2), developed (WP3 & WP4), and tested (WP6), all had regular online meetings to compensate all these difficulties almost every week during the first 28 months of the project (until Randomized Clinical Trial started). Thus, this challenge was known and dealt with by EMPOWER.

Other participants raised concerns that EMPOWER will conclude before its members can properly exploit its results. One participant worried that the technology developed by EMPOWER would not see further deployment once the project ends. They suggested that their junior colleagues are ready and able to devise follow-up studies but cannot do so because of funding limitations. They also lamented that said junior colleagues had spent three years learning how to deploy this technology in educational settings that accommodate neurodiverse children - and that these highly specialized skills may go to waste if they cannot complete studies that involve this technology after EMPOWER ends. Overall, the participants generally suggested that they wished Horizon Europe provided projects like EMPOWER with more time and resources at the beginning and end of projects to prepare and wrap up research.

3.2.2. Recommendations: abrupt beginnings and conclusion

The participants provided several solutions to the challenges mentioned above. Although some of these recommendations would require Horizon Europe to take action, others could be employed autonomously by projects comparable to EMPOWER. For instance, many participants suggested that projects like EMPOWER could develop and implement team-building exercises as soon as they start, to ensure members know each other's expertise. They implied that the first project meeting(s) should focus on learning what other researchers can and cannot do with their skill sets. They suggested that doing so would help members of different Work Packages know who they can ask for what and whether their requests are feasible, thus streamlining later collaboration efforts.

The participants suggested that dealing with a project's abrupt conclusion would be more challenging. For instance, it would likely require Horizon Europe to allocate funding for follow-up studies, ideally involving a smaller group of researchers from the same project with the expertise necessary to complete them. Nonetheless, this is especially pertinent for projects developing technologies for the neurodiverse community. The research done by EMPOWER (and projects like it) requires researchers working in the field to cultivate a level of emotional and ethical awareness of research participants' needs by repeatedly interacting with them. As such, learning how to deploy a technology under development in a manner that properly accommodates research participants takes a substantial amount of time (e.g., researchers need to complete numerous studies or pilots to get a grasp on what to expect and how to react in the field). Ideally, such follow-up studies would allow researchers with these highly specialized social skills to develop means to ensure other people or organizations can use the technology under development independently. Indeed, without such follow-up studies, some participants worried that these technologies may never see further deployment and, therefore, cannot benefit the community they were designed to support.

3.3.1. Challenges: interdisciplinary communication

Although this challenge pertains to how Horizon Europe projects are structured, it does differ from the previous challenge. The participants were clear that working in independent Work Packages focused on specific, disciplinarily related tasks was not a problem most of the time. However, they frequently communicated that collaborating with researchers with substantially different academic backgrounds was challenging. Many participants expressed that their colleagues from other Work Packages did not fully grasp what researchers with their academic backgrounds could or could not do with their skill sets and available resources (and vice-versa). Indeed, several implied that Work Packages “speak different languages” that are not mutually intelligible. For instance, one discussed how their colleagues from engineering assumed that psychologists from EMPOWER working in the field with neurodiverse children could deal with bugs or coding errors on the fly – even though this would be exceptionally difficult for them. Likewise, another suggested that their colleagues from the social sciences expected too much from the hardware or software used by EMPOWER. We should state here that the participants were sympathetic about this challenge and appreciated that it occurred because different disciplines simply have different approaches to research.

They were clear that the nature of the technology developed by EMPOWER required them to work this way (e.g., as members of independent disciplinary-focused teams) but consequently produced the challenges mentioned above. To briefly describe EMPOWER's organizational structure, every Work Package works on a different aspect of the said technology, using state-of-the-art disciplinary knowledge to collaboratively construct educational resources for neurodiverse children. As such, the participants expressed that they had to frequently translate scientific knowledge from one discipline to another (e.g., from engineering to psychology and vice-versa) to ensure their research could be used by other Work Packages. Doing so, took considerable time and effort. Understandably then, the participants expressed a strong desire to know substantially more about other Work Packages' capabilities so that they could coordinate with each other more effectively.

3.3.2. Recommendations: interdisciplinary communication

The participants were particularly appreciative of the bi-yearly meetings organized by EMPOWER. Indeed, they frequently mentioned that these meetings helped them understand the extent and limitations of their colleagues' disciplinary skillsets. For instance, several mentioned that they received exceptionally useful feedback from their colleagues working in different disciplines when they presented their results at these meetings. As such, they recommended that projects like EMPOWER ensure that every Work Package present their progress at these meetings and allocate ample time for them to receive feedback from their colleagues from other disciplines concerning how it will affect their research (e.g., does it align with standards from their field? Can they feasibly integrate said findings their workflow?). Indeed, they often suggested that more, perhaps, shorter meetings like this would be welcome.

The participants also regularly spoke about developing "simulations" or "role-playing" activities that explained what each Work Package could and could not do. For instance, several talked about setting up a simulation involving members from all Work Packages that demonstrated what it was like to use the technology developed by EMPOWER in the field. Some members would pretend to be children and teachers while others would play themselves and attempt to deploy the technology in a manner that follows EMPOWER protocol. Ideally, this would highlight the challenges social scientists working with EMPOWER face in the field and allow more technologically oriented

researchers to provide advice concerning the calibration of the various devices used by EMPOWER and data collection.

3.4.1. Challenge: recruitment and roles

Most participants expressed that recruiting staff with the right expertise, mindset, and willingness to work in a highly interdisciplinary environment involving a vulnerable population was among the key challenges they had faced. Many wished they had hired people earlier to help them with tasks they could not do alone or found ways to collaborate with researchers who could help EMPOWER more fully incorporate the neurodiverse community's experiences into its research design. For instance, one participant made it exceptionally clear that they would have struggled to meet their deadlines without the help of two research assistants they recruited from a master's program at their university.

Other participants, especially those from the social sciences and humanities, emphasized that they were lucky to have found junior staff who could produce high-quality research while prioritizing EMPOWER's primary goal in practice – i.e., supporting neurodiverse children and their caregivers via the platform under development. One mentioned, for instance, that their team working in the field with neurodiverse children had a “special gift to interact with kids” and always prioritized their care over data collection (e.g. would stop an experiment if they sensed a child was upset or distracted). The same participant suggested that finding people who understand that research plays second-fiddle to children's comfort is challenging because academia motivates researchers to focus on gathering high-quality, generalizable data for publication and consequently maintain rigid protocols in the field.

Several also mentioned that they wished Thomasin Coggins (the primary author of this report) had joined EMPOWER earlier. They emphasized that her research with Work Package 5, which focused on synthesizing literature from disability studies, neurodiversity rights, the ethics of technology, and participatory research design into actionable recommendations, had helped them recognize the risks and challenges of working with neurodiverse children more fully without having to allocate time to consult this literature themselves. Several conveyed that EMPOWER would have benefited

from hiring Thomasin Coggins (or someone with her research background) before the project started to ensure that she (or they) could help other members incorporate insights from the literature mentioned earlier into their protocol and research design from the get-go. However, due to various limitations, she began working with EMPOWER around half-way through the project.

Several participants also mentioned that they believed that EMPOWER should have more actively recruited researchers from the neurodiverse community – especially ones who had experience working on projects involving neurodiverse children. Doing so would have meant that such staff members could have provided advice based on their lived experience and academic background to guide EMPOWER’s research in directions that (ideally) aligned more precisely with the neurodiverse community’s interests. Indeed, one mentioned that EMPOWER had altered its research design significantly at least two times after receiving feedback from external parties with such knowledge. They indicated they would have preferred if staff members could have provided such feedback internally throughout the project (instead of exclusively relying on external consultations).

3.4.2. Recommendations: recruitment and roles

The participants collectively provided a picture of whom projects like EMPOWER should recruit. First and foremost, they emphasized that potential staff members should understand that projects like EMPOWER focus on helping the neurodiverse community above all else. For instance, empirical researchers should recognize that accommodating neurodiverse children in the field takes precedence over gathering rich data. Finding people who will prioritize the interests of a vulnerable population (in this case, neurodiverse children) even when doing so may compromise their results to some degree obviously poses challenges – because one cannot know if a potential employee holds and practices such beliefs until they complete a study. As such, the participants recommended recruiting people with experience working on projects that required them to modify their research to accommodate research participants. They suggested that purposely hiring people from the neurodiverse community would also help - especially if said recruits were willing and able to provide feedback based on their lived experiences.

They were also clear that projects should hire all essential staff members as early as possible. Most notably, they suggested that projects like EMPOWER need a junior ethics specialist on board from

the beginning. They frequently mentioned that they would have appreciated if Thomasin Coggins had conducted something akin to fieldwork and in-situ consultations. They envisioned her spending time with each Work Package as a participant observer (DeWalt & DeWalt, 2011; Spradley, 1980) who could provide them with ethical guidance when necessary. Due to time constraints, this could not happen. Again, finding someone with the expertise needed to conduct this kind of research is challenging. However, the participants implied that such junior ethics specialists should have a background in disability studies and be able to conduct qualitative empirical research independently.

3.5.1. Challenge: participatory Research Design

Although the participants appreciated that EMPOWER observed participatory research design practices, they often expressed that the project could have done so more effectively. Many mentioned that projects like EMPOWER should consult as many relevant stakeholders as possible when designing studies. While others discussed how they wished that EMPOWER had developed means to ensure that external parties representing the neurodiverse community could provide feedback during pivotal moments of the project. To be clear, the participants recognized that EMPOWER had successfully incorporated knowledge from its stakeholders and the neurodiverse community into its research design, following typical participatory research design practices (Schuller & Namioka, 1993; Elsabbagh et al, 2014; Flechter-Watson, 2019). However, they felt there was ample room for improvement. Several participants mentioned that they had to modify their research design after receiving feedback from stakeholders or representatives of the neurodiverse community. For instance, one participant mentioned that they did not realize that some neurodiverse children had difficulties using the input devices needed to play the games developed by EMPOWER so could not participate in studies using the EMPOWER platform without assistance from their teachers.

They expressed that they wished they had asked teachers whether all their students could use these devices independently beforehand to ensure their research design and protocol accommodated those who could not. The participants often communicated that it is wise to organize feedback session as earlier as possible when devising studies and wished they had done

this more frequently. Another participant spoke about how they had to change several aspects of a study they were developing after a group of anonymous consultants from Autism Europe reviewed it. They mentioned that these anonymous consultants provided extremely helpful advice and highlighted several issues they (the participant) had overlooked partly because they did not have the lived experience or knowledge of autism needed to recognize them.

The participants often mentioned that they would have preferred if EMPOWER had devised concrete means to incorporate knowledge from the neurodiverse community into their research design and protocol whenever they began planning a study. They conveyed that EMPOWER chiefly focused on gathering feedback from parents, teachers, and children during and after studies. However, it would have benefited from hearing from stakeholders and representatives of the neurodiverse community during the development of studies. They generally expressed that this would have simultaneously saved them time by ensuring they did not have to modify their studies halfway through or after their development and fulfilled one of the primary tenets of participatory research design (that affected communities are involved in studies' design from the start).

3.5.2. Recommendations: participatory Research Design

The participants offered straightforward advice concerning the challenges outlined above. Most notably, they suggested that projects like EMPOWER should organize feedback sessions with representatives of the neurodiverse community whenever they begin planning a study that involves neurodiverse participants. One of the chief challenges EMPOWER faced, which we have documented elsewhere², was that its primary research participants could not provide direct feedback on its research design because they were too young to understand it. The participants clarified that consulting neurodiverse adults during a study's planning stages helped deal with this challenge. They communicated they had received invaluable feedback that substantially improved the quality of their studies every time they had organized consultations of this kind. Several recommended that projects like EMPOWER should ask organizations representing the neurodiverse community's interests (e.g., Autism Europe) to review their draft research design every time they

² See deliverables 5.1 and 5.2.

complete it. Although this may require projects to allocate funds to pay for such consultations, the participants were adamant that this should happen. They mentioned that consulting neurodiverse children’s caretakers more frequently would have helped too. For instance, they suggested that researchers should not assume that all neurodiverse children can use technology under development and, therefore, should speak with their caregivers to learn about their capabilities before designing a study.

3.6. Summary

Underneath we have summarized the results provided in this deliverable in a 4x2 chart that contains phrases representing the challenges and recommendations the participants communicate to us.

Challenges	Recommendations
Abrupt Beginning and Conclusion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of team cohesion at beginning. • Need for follow-up studies 	Abrupt Beginning and Conclusion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early team building exercises • Contract extensions for junior staff members
Interdisciplinary Communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdisciplinary unintelligibility • Expectations of other disciplines’ skillsets. 	Inter-Disciplinary Communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular meetings focused on interdisciplinary feedback • Simulations
Recruitment and Roles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding empathic, respectful, and dedicated staff. • Need for junior ethics specialist 	Recruitment and Roles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on hiring staff who know how to adapt research around vulnerable community. • Hire a junior ethics specialist as early as possible.
Participatory Research Design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belated feedback from neurodiverse community 	Participatory Research Design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult neurodiverse adults during planning stages of research.

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Belated feedback from research participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Consult research participants during planning stages of research.
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4. Discussion

In this section, we provide recommendations based on our interpretation of the results outlined above. We developed these recommendations independently of the participants interview for this deliverable. As such, readers should treat them as Work Package 5's first attempt at creating a set "best practices" based on EMPOWER member's experiences. We have clustered them according to them themes used earlier for convenience.

4.1. Abrupt beginning and conclusions

We highly recommend that projects like EMPOWER develop means to foster communication between Work Packages as early as possible. For instance, each Work Package could give a presentation during early project wide-meetings that details the goals they aim to achieve in the near future, how they intend to meet them, the hurdles they expect to encounter, and how this might affect other Work Package's research. Furthermore, later project meetings could start with condensed, updated versions of such presentations, much like how many organizations regularly do "rounds"³ during meetings to ensure that staff members know what their colleagues are working on or struggling with. Ideally, these presentations would help Work Packages understand what they can expect from their colleagues.

Additionally, we recommend that projects like EMPOWER anticipate they will end abruptly and find ways to finance follow-up studies (ideally) before said projects begin. For instance, the authors of a project's proposal could help junior staff members who have the necessary expertise to complete such follow-up studies seek funding from governmental agencies or corporate partners. In the best-

³ E.g. every member or a representative of each Work Package briefly communicates a) what they're working on b) challenges they have recently faced and c) delays that may affect the project's overall progress.

case scenario, though, Horizon Europe would fund these studies and extend junior members' contracts. Alternatively, projects could apply for funding from grant providers that finance longer projects and permit contract extensions (for instance, the European Union Teaming for Excellence Call).

4.2. Interdisciplinary communication

As stated earlier, the participants believed that the bi-yearly meetings organized by EMPOWER helped them understand how their research affects other Work Packages (and vice-versa) and consequentially collaborate more effectively. Indeed, they expressed that they would have appreciated more meetings of this kind. As such we recommend that projects like EMPOWER structure these meetings to ensure a) every Work Package presents their progress and b) receives feedback from every other Work Package afterwards. Indeed, the participants were exceptionally clear that without such feedback their research may have continued down routes that would have eventually caused issues for their colleagues (e.g., because the results generated would have been difficult to integrate into their workflows due to disciplinary limitations). We also recommend organizing shorter, more frequent meetings of this kind if possible (e.g., one-hour meetings focusing on one Work Packages' progress study when needed)

Additionally, we highly recommend that projects that develop technology for the neurodiverse community (especially children) allocate time to "simulations" during their project-wide meetings. These simulations should demonstrate what it is like to deploy said technology in the field. Ideally, all Work Packages would contribute to these simulations' development. For instance, computer scientists could envision the bugs their colleagues may have to deal with and make sure the simulation reproduces them. Likewise, social scientists could tailor the simulations around the challenges they face when collecting data from neurodiverse children. Such simulations should highlight what each Work Package expects to go wrong during studies and aim to gather insights concerning how to deal with these challenges. If the technology under development cannot be deployed on-site, these simulations could use props instead.

4.3. Recruitment and roles

The participants regularly suggested that they would have appreciated if Work Package 5 had begun conducting qualitative empirical research before this deliverable. As stated earlier, this was not possible due to time constraints. As such, we highly recommend that projects like EMPOWER recruit a junior ethics specialist with social science skills before they begin. Ideally, this person would spend time with each Work Package to learn about their research and provide guidance in situ. For instance, they could attend other Work Packages meetings and observe studies to gather data and provide guidance in-situ. The Science and Technology Studies literature contains many resources that could help this person design their research (Latour & Woolgar, 1979; Stilgoe, 2015; de Boer, 2019). For instance, they could conduct an ethnography that documents what it is like to work on such highly interdisciplinary projects and the ethical challenges one should expect to face when developing resources for the neurodiverse community.

Regarding the recruitment other staff members, projects like EMPOWER could develop means to assess how possible staff members would react to ethical quandaries before hiring them. For instance, during recruitment interviews they could ask interviewees questions concerning how they would react to challenges associated with gathering and analyzing data from a vulnerable community. For social scientists, these questions could revolve around accommodating children in the field (e.g., “what would you do if a child wanted to do something else instead of use the technology under development” or “how would you react to a child who seems distressed?”). Whereas for more technologically oriented recruits, these questions could focus on dealing with limited data and collaborating with social scientists (e.g., “can you think of ways to alter your research when your colleagues working in the field cannot gather the data you expected?” or “how would you respond to your colleagues when they told you that their field research did not go according to plan and therefore did not generate the data you anticipated?”).

4.4. Participatory research design

We highly recommend that projects like EMPOWER recruit an external group of advisors representing the neurodiverse community's interests to review their research design and protocol as early as possible. The participants regularly mentioned that several NGOs based in the European Union offer such consultations, most notably Autism Europe. Following our participants advice, we believe that projects like EMPOWER should specify in their proposal that they will establish an external committee to review their work. Doing so would simultaneously communicate that they need funding to establish this committee and are committed to creating it. Ideally, this group would provide written or in-person feedback concerning the neurodiverse communities' experiences and needs during the planning phases of all studies.

Regarding stakeholder feedback, we recommend that projects like EMPOWER complete informal demo sessions where a small group of end-users experience using the technology under development before conducting studies that deploy it. The participants regularly expressed that they had not accurately anticipated how end-users would respond to the technology used by EMPOWER and wished they had known about this earlier. For instance, neurodiverse children's teachers and parents can provide expert advice concerning whether their students and children can use devices as researchers expect them to. It is, therefore, wise to informally ask them to inspect technologies under development before deploying them in experimental settings. Researchers could also invite some children to play with said technologies to assess their useability.

5. Conclusion

In this deliverable, we presented the results of the first round of semi-structured interviews we plan to conduct with members of EMPOWER to create a set of best practices that projects like EMPOWER may use to guide their research. We interviewed EMPOWER's ethical reflection team to do so (n=7). This low number of participants means that the results presented do not represent the experiences of EMPOWER's entire team. We intend to deal with this limitation by interviewing as many members of EMPOWER as possible over the next few months. Because she will conduct the interviews, we cannot use this format to gather insights concerning Thomasin Coggins' experiences working with EMPOWER. As such, she will provide a report covering the challenges she faced and

the recommendations she would give to other researchers in her position in deliverable 5.4 and possibly the research paper we intend to complete.

As stated earlier, we will use these interviews to develop Deliverable 5.4 and a research paper. Both documents will include and build on the insights presented in this deliverable. Indeed, we believe that developing Deliverable 5.3 has provided us with ample means to complete both projects. Most notably, the interview guide we used successfully elicited responses from participants concerning the chief challenges and recommendations they believe researchers working on projects like EMPOWER should be aware of. Likewise, we believe the coding scheme we developed effectively clusters these insights into logical and comprehensible themes. Moving forward, we will use both research aids to create a complete set of best practices that reflect EMPOWER members' experiences working in a highly interdisciplinary environment while developing educational resources for neurodiverse children.

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